

1066-P: Sleep Habits and Their Impact on CGM Parameters in Patients with Type 1 Diabetes **FREE**

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Introduction & Objective: Inadequate sleep can have a negative impact on health in many ways, not least on glycemic control. Our aim was to demonstrate the impact of poor sleep habits on type 1 diabetes (T1DM) control, as these data are lacking.

Methods: Eighty-five patients with T1DM > 10 years aged 30-67 years were enrolled in the study. All patients completed the Munich Chronotype Questionnaire (MCTQ), which focused on sleep timing on workdays and free days (difference is defined as social jetlag) and the determination of their own chronotype (individual sleep-wake behavior). To objectively assess sleep habits, all patients were monitored with a smart watch for two weeks and sleep parameters (REM, deep, light and total sleep) were analyzed. Both device data and MCTQ results were compared with CGM parameters.

Results: The average duration of total sleep was 7.2 ± 0.9 , deep sleep 0.7 ± 0.2 , REM sleep 1.3 ± 0.4 and light sleep 4.5 ± 0.8 hours. The duration of sleep from smartwatch strongly correlated with the results of the sleep-focused MCTQ questions ($r=0.44$, $p<0.001$). Patients with more hypoglycemic events slept less overall ($r=-0.28$, $p=0.015$). Those who slept less had higher mean sensor glucose levels ($r=-0.23$, $p=0.043$), and furthermore, deep sleep was negatively correlated with higher glycemic variability ($r=-0.23$, $p=0.04$). We found that the presence of neuropathy ($r=-0.28$, $p=0.01$), retinopathy ($r=-0.27$, $p=0.01$) and albuminuria ($r=-0.36$, $p=0.01$) correlated with shorter deep sleep. Both hypertension ($r=-0.25$, $p=0.02$) and higher HbA1c ($r=-0.27$, $p=0.017$) were associated with shorter REM sleep. Late chronotypes were also correlated with less REM sleep ($r=-0.24$, $p=0.028$). In addition, those with higher social jetlag had shorter total and light sleep ($r=-0.28$, $p=0.01$).

Conclusion: Our study showed that T1DM patients with microvascular complications and poorer DM control had significantly worse sleep quality. In addition, our subjects were objectively accurate in their responses about sleep habits.

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Disclosure

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